

Working Paper

National Recovery and Resilience Plans

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Abstract: Beyond its remarkable financial size, the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) introduces an innovative ‘demand-driven and performance-based’ governance design centred on National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs) agreed between Member States, the Commission, and the Council. This chapter analyzes the practical functioning of this new governance design, drawing on an in-depth study of the drafting, implementation, and monitoring of NRRPs in eleven Member States. It assesses how far governments took ownership of the plans, their inclusiveness, and the Commission’s role in their negotiation. It then examines how the NRRPs have affected domestic policy making, what obstacles have arisen in their implementation, and how monitoring and assessment by the Commission works in practice, with particular attention to its interpretive flexibility, administrative load, and responsiveness to unanticipated changes in circumstances. The chapter concludes by assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the RRF governance model, together with the implications for future EU policy.

Keywords: European Union governance, Europeanization, national ownership, performance-based financing, Recovery and Resilience Facility, stakeholder inclusion

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), which forms the core of the NextGenerationEU package adopted in response to the Covid-19 pandemic, has been widely hailed as a breakthrough for European integration. The RRF stands out for its remarkable size (€ 723 billion at current prices over six years from 2021 to 2026), its unprecedented combination of non-repayable grants and loans to Member States (MSs), and its financing through common European Union (EU) borrowing.¹ But beyond its ambitious quantitative scope, the RRF also introduces a series of governance innovations, which have been designed to address the perceived limitations of previous EU policies seeking to promote national reforms. First, in contrast to the Country-Specific Recommendations (CSRs) issued to MSs under the European Semester of socio-economic policy coordination, the RRF links structural reforms with complementary investments aimed at creating political momentum for their implementation through the provision of positive financial incentives. Second, in contrast to the Economic Adjustment Programmes and Memoranda of Understanding imposed on bail-out countries during the euro crisis, the RRF is a ‘demand-driven’ process, aimed at fostering ‘national ownership’ of reforms through the drafting of National Recovery and Resilience Plans (NRRPs) jointly with Member States and tailored to their needs. Third, in contrast to the Cohesion Policy Funds (CPF), the RRF is designed as a ‘performance-based’ instrument, in which periodic payments to Member States are based on the fulfilment of preagreed milestones and targets (M&Ts) rather than reimbursement of eligible costs incurred.²

The RRF’s innovative governance design has inspired widespread debate about its potential application to other EU policies. Already, the RRF framework has been extended to address the energy crisis triggered by the invasion of Ukraine through the REPowerEU programme, which encourages Member States to add new reforms and investments to their NRRPs, in order to reduce dependence on Russian fossil fuels, accelerate the clean energy transition, and alleviate energy poverty, financed by additional grants and repurposing of unclaimed RRF loans.³ There is also a lively discussion ongoing within Brussels policy circles about whether the RRF governance model should be extended to other EU programmes funded through the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), notably the CPF.⁴ The Commission has likewise explicitly drawn inspiration from the RRF

¹ On the financial novelty of the RRF and its significance for European integration, see Federico Fabbrini, *EU Fiscal Capacity: Legal Integration After Covid-19 and the War in Ukraine* (Oxford University Press, 2022); and the chapter by Stefania Baroncelli, this volume.

² On the innovative governance design of the RRF and its critical relationship to other EU policy instruments, see Commission, *Recovery and Resilience Facility: Two years on. A unique instrument at the heart of the EU’s green and digital transformation* (Communication) COM (2023) 99 final; and for a fuller analysis, Jonathan Zeitlin, David Bokhorst, and Edgars Eihmanis, *Governing the RRF: Drafting, Implementing, and Monitoring National Recovery and Resilience Plans as an Interactive Multilevel Process* (Recovery Watch Policy Study, Foundation for European Progressive Studies [FEPS], 2023) <<https://feps-europe.eu/publication/governing-the-rrf/>> 12-13. For a detailed comparison between the RRF and the CPF, which qualifies the contrast between the two governance models, see Jonathan Zeitlin, David Bokhorst, and Edgars Eihmanis, ‘Rethinking the Governance and Delivery of the Cohesion Policy Funds: Is the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) a Model?’ (academic paper prepared for the 8th meeting of the High-Level Group on the Future of Cohesion Policy, Commission DG REGIO, 2023), <https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/how/future-cohesion-policy_en>. See also the chapter by Niall Moran in this volume.

³ COM (2023) 99 final 5-6; and see also the chapter by Rosalba Famà in this volume. A similar governance approach underlies the Social Climate Fund, which will co-finance temporary income support measures and long-term structural investments to support the energy transition by helping vulnerable citizens most affected by energy and transport poverty, based on national ‘social climate plans’: Regulation (EU) 2023/955 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 establishing a Social Climate Fund and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, [2023] OJ L 130/1.

⁴ See, for example, Commission, DG REGIO, ‘Revisiting the delivery mode of Cohesion Policy’, (issue paper for the 8th meeting of the High-Level Group on the Future of Cohesion Policy, 2023), <https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/how/future-cohesion-policy_en>; European Court of Auditors (ECA) *EU*

in its recent proposals for reform of the EU's economic governance framework, in which national medium-term fiscal-structural plans would play a central role.⁵

Understanding the effectiveness and legitimacy of the RRF's governance design and operation is thus of utmost importance for scholars and policy makers alike. The RRF's success will ultimately depend on the extent to which the NRRPs fulfil the expectations of its governance design by advancing the reform and investment objectives jointly agreed between national governments and the Commission. In this chapter, we analyze how the NRRPs have been drafted and are now being implemented, as well as how they are being monitored, assessed, and in some cases revised, at both national and EU levels. More specifically, we assess the extent to which governments took ownership of the plans, the inclusiveness of their drafting, and the role of the Commission in steering the process. We then go on to examine how the NRRPs have affected domestic policy making, what obstacles have arisen in the implementation process, and how monitoring and assessment of the M&Ts by the Commission works in practice, with particular attention to its interpretive flexibility, administrative load, and responsiveness to unanticipated changes in circumstances. The chapter concludes by assessing the strengths and weaknesses of the NRRPs and the RRF governance model more broadly, while drawing out the implications for future EU policy.

In addition to the broader literature on the NRRPs, most of which focuses on their policy content and potential impact rather than their practical operation,⁶ this chapter draws heavily on the findings of an in-depth comparative study of the drafting, implementation, and monitoring of national plans in eight MSs (Belgium, Croatia, Estonia, Italy, Latvia, Portugal, Slovakia, and Spain), which together account for more than half of all RRF grant funding. Apart from Belgium, this study deliberately focused on southern and eastern European countries which are the largest beneficiaries of the RRF (in terms of grants and loans relative to GDP, ranging from 3% for Estonia and 5.6% for Latvia to 11% for Croatia and Italy), where both the domestic impact of the NRRPs and the potential influence of the Commission might be expected to be strongest. By way of contrast, we also examined the drafting of the NRRPs in three additional northern MSs (Austria, Germany, and the Netherlands, where RRF funding was much lower in relation to GDP (less than 1%), though quite substantial both in absolute terms and as a share of total RRF grants (just over 10%).⁷

For reasons of tractability, as well as the substantive expertise of the research team, this study focused primarily on the social dimension of the NRRPs, broadly defined to include employment and skills, education and childcare, health and long-term care, as well as social inclusion and social protection,

financing through cohesion policy and the Recovery and Resilience Facility: a comparative analysis (Review 01, Publications Office of the EU, 2023); Zeitlin et al. 'Rethinking the Governance and Delivery Model of the Cohesion Policy Funds' (n 2).

⁵ Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on the effective coordination of economic policies and multilateral budgetary surveillance and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1466/97' COM (2023) 240 final.

⁶ For an extensive set of individual country studies, see 'The Next Generation EU in action: Impact of social and labour policies', [2021] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal. For other comparative studies that examine the drafting and to a much lesser extent implementation of the NRRPs, see David Bokhorst and Francesco Corti 'Governing Europe's Recovery and Resilience Facility: Between discipline and discretion' [2023] Government and Opposition 1; Francesco Corti and Patrik Vesán 'From austerity-conditionality towards a new investment-led growth strategy: Social Europe after the Recovery and Resilience Facility' [2023] Social Policy and Administration 1; Joan Miró, Marcello Natili, and Waltraud Schelkle 'Money makes the world go Round: How much difference do Recovery and Resilience Plans make to EU reform governance?' [2023] JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies 1; Mario Munta, Brigitte Pircher, and Sonja Becker 'Ownership of national recovery plans: next generation EU and democratic legitimacy' [2023] Journal of European Public Policy 1; Nils Oellerich and Jasper P. Simons 'Supranational modernization or national partisanship? Explaining variation in Recovery and Resilience Plans in Central and Eastern Europe' [2023] Journal of European Public Policy 1.

⁷ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2). For figures on RRF funding relative to GDP in these countries, see *ibid.* p. 3 and Annex 1; the initial grant allocations referred to in these figures were revised upwards or downwards in 2022 based on Member States' rate of economic recovery following the pandemic.

which according to the Commission's scoreboard, account for an average of 28% of planned RRF spending across Member States.⁸ In addition, however, we also looked at major reforms and investments in other policy fields, such as liberalization of closed professions and water management, where these emerged as especially significant in our country cases. Alongside extensive documentary and media analysis, the study is based on c. 60 interviews with national and Commission officials directly involved with the NRRPs, as well as other relevant domestic stakeholders.⁹

This chapter is structured as follows. Section 2 analyzes the drafting and negotiation of the NRRPs, examining in sequence their level of national ownership and ambition, the involvement of domestic stakeholders, and the role of the Commission in this process. Section 3 deals with the implementation and monitoring of the national Plans, considering sequentially their impact on domestic policy making, stakeholder exclusion as a source of implementation problems, and their monitoring and assessment by the Commission. The conclusion weighs up the strengths and weaknesses of the RRF governance model, including the NRRPs, and briefly discusses its possible impact on future EU policy.

2. DRAFTING THE NRRPs

The RRF is demand-driven, insofar as MSs draft the NRRPs and propose integrated packages of reforms and investments, in consultation with the Commission. As the Commission argues, MSs 'have flexibility in designing and implementing the measures in a way that suits their national conditions, which increases their ownership of plans.'¹⁰ At the same time, the RRF Regulation stipulates that these plans must also meet a series of specific requirements set by the EU. Each plan should show how it represents 'a comprehensive and adequately balanced response to the economic and social situation of the Member State concerned', involving a coherent mix of investments and reforms, while contributing appropriately to the recovery and enhanced resilience of the Union through support for measures in key policy areas of European relevance (the so-called 'six pillars': green transition; digital transformation; smart, sustainable, and inclusive growth; social and territorial cohesion; health and economic, social, and institutional resilience; and policies for the next generation). The NRRPs must further devote minimum percentages of expenditure to the green and digital transitions (37% and 20%, respectively), and respect the principle of Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) to the EU's environmental objectives. In addition, the plans must demonstrate how they contribute to the implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR), 'thereby enhancing the economic, social, and territorial coherence within the Union', and effectively address all or a significant subset of challenges identified in the relevant country-specific recommendations' (CSRs) issued under the European Semester.¹¹

The RRF Regulation further stipulates that the NRRPs 'should set out the detailed set of measures for [their] monitoring and implementation, including targets and milestones and estimated costs', as part of the Facility's performance-based financing design, in which the release of funds is contingent on MSs' satisfactory fulfilment of preagreed M&Ts.¹² Here, too, the Commission argues that because these 'milestones and targets are designed individually to fit the specific investment and reforms the

⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/recovery-and-resilience-scoreboard/index.html>.

⁹ For further information on the design and methodology of this study, see Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 10-11; and for a full but anonymized list of interviewees, see *ibid* Annex 3

¹⁰ COM (2023) 99 final 2.

¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and the Council of 12 February 2021 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility [2021] OJ L 57/17, recital 39 and Art. 18.4. On the DNSH principle, see Commission, 'Technical guidance on the application of "do no significant harm" under the Recovery and Resilience Facility regulation' [2021] OJ C 58/1.

¹² RRF Regulation (n 9) recitals 39, 51-52.

Member States commit to implement, this gives them full ownership to ensure a successful delivery.¹³

Finally, the RRF Regulation requires MSs to put in place effective arrangements for monitoring and implementing the plan, as well as for preventing and detecting corruption and fraud, including a single point of contact with the Commission; and to demonstrate that the estimated costs of the plan are reasonable and proportional to the expected impact and do not involve double funding from other EU programmes.¹⁴

Based on these criteria, the Commission was given responsibility for assessing the NRRPs and proposing to the Council draft Implementing Decisions (CIDs) for approval through a comitology procedure, as well as for agreeing Operating Arrangements bilaterally with MSs for the implementation of their plans, including specific indicators for verification of M&Ts to be used in approving periodic payment requests.¹⁵

2.1 Ownership and Ambition of National Plans

Whereas the Commission assessed all plans of MSs covered in our study as contributing sufficiently to addressing a significant subset of CSRs, we found that the level of ambition and national ownership of the NRRPs varied considerably. In a number of countries, notably Portugal, Spain, Croatia, and Slovakia, MSs presented ambitious recovery and resilience plans with a coherent balance between investments and reforms, addressing the full set of CSRs and sometimes going beyond them in the social field, as in the case of pension adequacy, long-term care, and inclusion of people with disabilities in Spain and Croatia.¹⁶ In Italy, the NRRP entails a very extensive programme of investment in the modernization of infrastructure and public services, accompanied by major reforms of public administration, justice, and competition rules, but leaves significant gaps in addressing CSRs and vulnerabilities in the social field, notably in terms of measures to reduce poverty and enhance inclusion among precarious workers.¹⁷ The Belgian Plan addresses many but not all of the CSRs, while including some additional measures in areas such as social housing, childcare, and long-term care, but its precision, coherence, and level of ambition were criticized by the Commission.¹⁸ Estonia and Latvia, which like Belgium received lower (relative) grant allocations than the other MSs in our study, were initially reluctant to link investments to reforms, and only agreed to include significant social measures, such as indexation of the minimum income in LV or improvements in long-term care in EE, at the insistence of the Commission, resulting in a lower level of national ownership for their Plans.¹⁹ In our three northern contrast cases (Austria, Germany, and the

¹³ COM (2023) 99 1.

¹⁴ RRF Regulation (n 9) Art 18.4.

¹⁵ Ibid. Arts. 19-20 and Annex 5.

¹⁶ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 17-20; see also Francesco Corti, Alessandro Liscai, and Tomas Ruiz 'The Recovery and Resilience Facility: boosting investment in social infrastructure in Europe?' [2022] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal 1; Corti and Vesan (n 6); Ana M. Guillén, Margarita León, and Emmanuele Pavolini 'Are "carrots" better than "sticks"?' New EU conditionality and social investment policies in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic in Italy and Spain' [2022] Comparative European Politics 1; Ane Aranguiz 'National Recovery and Resilience Plan: Spain' [2022] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal 1; Ana Teresa Ribeiro 'National Recovery and Resilience Plan: Portugal' [2022] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal 1; Sandra Laleta 'National Recovery and Resilience Plan: Croatia' [2022] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal 1.

¹⁷ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 21; see also Corti et al. (n 12) 26; Corti and Vesan (n 6) Table A5 and Annex 2 Table 4; Guillén et al. (n 12); Marco Barbieri and Dario Guarascio 'La pandemia e la necessità di reformare il sistema degli ammortizzatori sociali' [2021] Politiche Sociali/Social Policies 493; Edoardo Ales 'National Recovery and Resilience Plan: Italy' [2022] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal 1; special issue [2021] on the NRRP of the Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche.

¹⁸ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 22-23; see also Corti and Vesan (n 6) 9-10; Pieter Pecinovskiy 'National Recovery and Resilience Plan: Belgium' [2022] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal 1.

¹⁹ Ibid 24-25; see also Linda Romele 'National Recovery and Resilience Plan: Latvia' [2022] 15 (special issue) Italian Labour Law e-Journal 1.

Netherlands), levels of ambition in their Plans were much lower across the board, leaving a substantial set of CSRs wholly or largely unaddressed, including in the social domain. The Netherlands and Germany in particular decided to dedicate all or most (respectively) of their funding to carry out projects which had already been included and budgeted in existing national plans, backdating a substantial portion of spending to 2020 as permitted by the RRF Regulation, thereby minimizing the ownership and impact of their Plans within and beyond national administrations.²⁰

Comparing these MSs, a number of country-specific factors appear to explain the variations observed in the level of ambition and national ownership in the NRRPs. First, the combination of large RRF funding (relative to GDP) with high fiscal debt constraints encouraged ambitious investment and reform plans (Portugal, Spain, Italy, and to a lesser extent Belgium, which combined a high debt constraint with lower RRF funding). This pattern was intensified in MSs that had suffered from austerity and reductions in social and labour rights during the decade following the euro crisis, and which had new or recently re-elected left-wing government coalitions (Portugal, Spain). A similar activist pattern can also be observed in less heavily fiscally constrained countries with new governments anxious to break with past policies and establish a reform-oriented profile, including in the social domain, taking advantage of high RRF funding (Croatia, Slovakia). Conversely, a lower relative size of grants, coupled with low fiscal constraints, high availability of cohesion policy funding, and economically liberal governments and electorates led to socially unambitious plans with weak domestic ownership, especially where reform measures demanded ongoing expenditures from the national budget, which cannot be financed from the RRF (Latvia, Estonia). In our northern contrast cases (Austria, Germany, the Netherlands), as in the Baltics, low relative RRF grant funding, coupled with weak fiscal constraints, resulted in unambitious plans with limited national ownership, though ideological issues around growth strategies and social policy did not appear to have played a similar role in these countries.²¹

2.2 Involvement of domestic stakeholders

Both the RRF regulation and the Commission's guidance are very clear about the need to consult local and regional authorities, social partners, civil society organizations, and other relevant stakeholders in the drafting process, and to report on how their input was reflected in the drafting process.²² Despite these exhortations, however, a series of EU-level assessments, by the Committee of the Regions (CoR), Eurofound, and the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) among others unanimously agree that stakeholder involvement in drafting the NRRPs was extremely limited, both on the side of local and regional authorities and on that of social partners and civil society.²³ In most MSs, as our study confirms, national governments typically stuck to the formal requirements to consult stakeholders, but the substantive quality of the process was low. Plans were typically drafted in a highly centralized manner under heavy time constraints by small groups attached to Prime Minister's Offices and Ministries of Finance. Exceptions to this broader pattern among the countries covered in our study include Portugal, where the NRRP built on an earlier plan, which involved extensive public consultation; Belgium, where the NRRP was assembled from separate regional plans and consultations with social partners based on the strong framework for their involvement developed under the European Semester; and to a lesser extent Spain, where the autonomous regional

²⁰ Ibid. 26-7; see also Bokhorst and Corti (n 6); Corti et al. (n 12) 26-27; Corti and Vesan (n 6) 8-10.

²¹ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 1) 26-7 and Annex 1, Tables 1 and 3.

²² RRF Regulation (n 9) Art. 18.4(q); Commission 'Guidance to member states on Recovery and Resilience Plans' SWD (2021) 12 final 47. It should be noted, however, that stakeholder consultation in the drafting process did not form part of the official criteria for the Commission's assessment of the NRRPs: RRF Regulation (n9) Annex V.

²³ CoR, Regional and local authorities and the national recovery and resilience plans (Publications Office of the EU, 2021); Eurofound Involvement of social partners in the national recovery and resilience plans (Publications Office of the EU, 2022); EESC 'Resolution of the EESC on Involvement of Organised Civil Society in the National Recovery and Resilience Plans – What works and what does not?' [2021] OJ C 155/01. For additional references, see Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) n 65.

communities were consulted on issues falling within their competences through the established system of sectoral conferences. Conversely, in Italy, where regions also have constitutional responsibilities for specific policy areas, they were nonetheless largely marginalized by successive governments in the drafting of the NRRP.²⁴

2.3 The Commission's Role in the Drafting Process

In the MSs covered by our study, the Commission's role in the drafting of the NRRPs, which typically involved numerous meetings and intensive negotiations with national officials, seems for the most part to have been closely aligned with the responsibilities assigned to it in the RRF Regulation, namely to ensure the relevance and coherence of the plans, the effectiveness of coordination and monitoring arrangements, and the operationalization of milestones and targets, while fully respecting national ownership. In many cases, the Commission went beyond this gatekeeper role, serving as an informal consultant to MSs to ensure that their plans could be effectively implemented, for example by advising national administrations to reduce and simplify the number of milestones and targets or to extend the timetable for project completion. Regarding investments, the Commission seems to have been prepared to defer to MS preferences in the name of promoting national ownership, so long as these conformed to RRF requirements, even where it was critical of the specific choices involved (such as a large dam project in Portugal or a massive new capital city hospital in Estonia), pushing at most for marginal shifts in the allocation of funds within and between projects. Concerning reforms, the Commission played a stronger role in shaping and steering the drafting of the NRRPs, both in pressing for a balance between reforms and investments where this was initially missing in some national plans (e.g. Italy, Croatia, Latvia, Estonia) and in pushing for measures to address key CSRs, especially where critical vulnerabilities were identified in the Social Scoreboard developed for monitoring the EPSR.²⁵ The most contentious interactions concerned MSs that combined longstanding resistance to implementing social CSRs with poor performance on the EPSR Social Scoreboard indicators (Latvia and Estonia). There the Commission insisted on inclusion of specific reforms addressing these issues in the NRRPs as a condition of their approval, despite the fact that the measures in question required ongoing expenditures from the national budget which could not be financed by the RRF. In most cases, however, the Commission was prepared to defer to domestic policy choices to enhance national ownership of reforms, while ensuring that the specific measures proposed would not run contrary to specific recommendations in the CSRs and that their underlying objective would be addressed through a different route, as for example with pension reforms in Spain and Croatia.²⁶

The most important disparities between the Commission's role in the drafting of the NRRPs across MSs uncovered in our study concerned the extent to which it pressed them to address the full set of CSRs. While the Commission typically started negotiations with the ambition to see all CSRs addressed as far as possible, in countries that received a low relative amount of grant funding, its leverage to achieve this was often much smaller. Thus as noted in section 2.1 above, northern MS like the Netherlands, Belgium, and Austria were permitted to respond shallowly to a substantial number of CSRs, or as in Germany leave many almost completely unaddressed.²⁷ But even among countries that received larger relative grant allocations from the RRF, there were considerable variations in how far the Commission insisted that they address the full set of CSR challenges in their

²⁴ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 27-31. On the marginalization of the Italian regions in the drafting of the NRRP, see also Stefania Profeti and Brunetta Baldi, 'Le regioni italiane e il PNRR: la (vana) ricerca di canali d'accesso all'agenda' [2021] *Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche* 431.

²⁵ The official criteria for the Commission's assessment of NRRPs include 'contributing to improving the levels of the indicators of [the] Social Scoreboard': RRF Regulation (n 9), Annex 5, par. 2.3. For national rankings on the Social Scoreboard indicators across the MSs covered in this study, see Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) Annex 1, Table 4.

²⁶ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 31-39; see also the chapter by Maria Patrín in this volume. On the Commission's role in the negotiation of reforms in the Italian and Spanish Plans, see also Miró et al. (n 6).

²⁷ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 35, 37-38.

NRRPs. In Croatia, for example, the Commission pressed successfully for the national plan to address all CSRs, while in Estonia and Latvia, as observed above, Commission officials likewise insisted that social challenges identified in the CSRs be addressed in the NRRPs as a condition of their approval, despite their lower relative level of RRF grant funding.²⁸ By contrast, in Italy, whose relative RRF grant funding is similar to Croatia's, the Commission did not require the government to address all CSRs, despite substantial coverage gaps, including vulnerabilities identified as critical in the EPSR Social Scoreboard.²⁹ While the evidence we collected did not specifically address the question of how to explain these disparities in the treatment of MSs, it is difficult to avoid the conclusion that country size and other political considerations may have played a contributory role.³⁰

3. IMPLEMENTING AND MONITORING THE NRRPS

3.1 Impact of NRRP Implementation on Domestic Policy Making

The most visible and widespread effect of the NRRPs on domestic policy making has been to reinforce the centralization of authority and decision making within national governments. Such centralization is a natural consequence of the RRF's requirements for MSs to establish effective domestic arrangements for implementing and monitoring NRRP commitments and to maintain a single national point of contact for verifying the fulfilment of the relevant M&Ts in support of periodic payment requests. Their effectiveness formed a crucial criterion for the Commission's assessment of the NRRPs, which were further elaborated and made binding in the CIDs and Operational Arrangements. The MSs covered in our study differed in the extent to which they created new bodies to perform the coordination, monitoring, reporting, and auditing functions required for NRRP implementation or assigned them to existing administrative units. But in all cases the result of these arrangements has been to concentrate authority in the hands of Prime Minister's Offices and Ministries of Finance and to centralize decision making at the national level, albeit with some cross-country variation (lower in Belgium, Portugal, and Spain, higher in Italy and Croatia).³¹

A major attraction of the RRF's performance-based financing model for national governments is the enhanced leverage for overcoming domestic opposition to controversial reforms, while smoothing their passage and amplifying their impact through complementary investments. The tight linkage between fulfilment of milestones and targets on the one hand, and approval of payment requests on the other also creates pressures on administrative actors at local and regional as well as central levels to streamline the delivery of investments. In a number of cases, national governments included key elements of their political programmes in the NRRPs as an explicit strategy of 'hand tying' or '*vincolo esterno*' aimed at using the external constraint of RRF commitments as a critical resource in getting them through the policy process. Prominent examples of the effectiveness of this strategy among the countries covered in our study included the liberalisation of closed professions in Portugal and pension reform in Slovakia, both of which were pushed through parliament on the eve of an impending payment request. In some countries like Italy and Spain, national officials see the RRF's performance-based financing and monitoring system as a valuable lever for accelerating the approval and implementation of investment projects, including by other levels of government. In others, such as Croatia and Slovakia, some of our interviewees also saw the performance-based management system of the RRF not only as a source of leverage, but also as an accountability mechanism for ensuring that political commitments are made concrete and visible to the media and the public, with clear deadlines for delivery. At the same time, however, the dependency of RRF payment requests on the timely completion of specific milestones and targets can also backfire by creating opportunities for hold-up and side-payment demands by domestic veto players, as in the case of justice reforms in

²⁸ Ibid 33, 35-37.

²⁹ Ibid 34.

³⁰ Ibid 39.

³¹ Ibid 42.

Slovakia. In the longer term, there is a serious risk that as governments change and national ownership of Plan objectives declines, the *vincolo esterno* strategy of tying reform commitments to external constraints will start to yield diminishing or even negative returns, as occurred in the past in Italy, where the strategy originated during preparations for euro membership in the 1990s.³²

3.2 Stakeholder Exclusion as a Source of Implementation Problems

In most MSs, as observed in section 2.2 above, involvement of domestic stakeholders such as social partners and local and regional authorities in the drafting of the NRRPs was extremely limited. In some cases, like that of labour market reform in Croatia, the limited involvement of societal stakeholders in the drafting of M&Ts has been corrected during the implementation phase, thereby ensuring support from both unions and employers. In others, however, failure to ensure political buy-in from domestic stakeholders has created more serious problems in the implementation of promised reforms, as with water management in Croatia, where the municipalities who had not been properly consulted in advance were able to block a proposed reorganization by starting legal proceedings in front of the Constitutional Court. Regarding investments, the central problem resulting from inadequate involvement of key stakeholders in the planning process is reduced implementability of the projects themselves. Examples include childcare expansion in Spain, where regions have complained that the distribution criteria of the funds fail to take account of the existing local mix of public and private providers, and in Italy, where municipalities responsible for implementation lack administrative and financial capacity to cope with tender deadlines and co-funding requirements.³³

3.3 Monitoring Milestones and Targets

The Commission's role in the monitoring phase is even greater than during the drafting process, as it must assess whether M&Ts have been sufficiently fulfilled to warrant periodic payments to MS. Yet the Commission is not the final decision maker for the approval of NRRP payment requests. As laid down in the RRF Regulation, the Commission's preliminary assessment of the satisfactory fulfilment of the M&Ts underlying these payments is subject to review by the Economic and Financial Committee (EFC), an advisory body to the Council composed of high officials from national finance and economics ministries. The Commission must take account of the EFC's opinion in its final implementing decision on each payment request, which must in turn be approved by a comitology committee of MS representatives. If one or more MS disagree with a positive opinion by the EFC, considering that 'there are serious deviations from the satisfactory fulfilment of the relevant milestones and targets', they may escalate the issue to the European Council for further discussion, until which time (normally a maximum of three months) the decision is suspended.³⁴ The Commission is thus under considerable pressure to ensure precision in justifying payment requests

³² Ibid 43-45. On the origins and declining effectiveness of the *vincolo esterno* strategy in Italy, see Kenneth Dyson and Kevin Featherstone 'Italy and EMU as a "vincolo esterno": Empowering the technocrats, transforming the state' (2007) [2] *South European Politics and Society* 272; Erik Jones 'Relations with Europe: Beyond the *vincolo esterno*' (2017) [32] *Italian Politics* 51.

³³ Ibid 46-47; on implementation problems arising from the insufficient involvement of local and regional authorities in the design of childcare expansion plans in Spain and Italy, see also Francesco Corti, Christian Morabito, Tomas Ruiz, and Patrizia Luongo, *The Role of the Recovery and Resilience Facility in Strengthening Childcare Policies* (Recovery Watch Policy Study, FEPS, 2022) <<https://feps-europe.eu/publication/the-role-of-the-recovery-and-resilience-facility-in-strengthening-childcare-policies/>> 23, 32, 38. In Italy, these local implementation problems have led to a reduction in the target for nursery places to be created from 264,480 to 150,000 in the revised version of the NRRP recently accepted by the Commission: see Giuseppe Colombo, 'Pnrr, la promessa tradita degli asili' (*La Repubblica*, Rome 23 November 2023) <https://www.repubblica.it/economia/2023/11/26/news/pnrr_italia_progetti_asili-421249297/>.

³⁴ RRF Regulation (n 9) recital 52, Art. 24; see also the chapter by Patrin in this volume. This last step is the so-called 'emergency brake', which has so far never been activated, inserted in the RRF arrangements at the insistence of the Netherlands during negotiations in the July 2020 European Council over the NextGenEU package: see Sandrino Smeets and Femke Bekius, 'Coordination and Control in European Council Centred Governance. The Netherlands and the Covid Recovery Fund' *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies* (2022) 1.

not only from the Council as the ultimate decider, but also from the ECA, which has inserted itself prominently in the process, issuing a series of detailed recommendations for tightening up and formalizing the procedures for verifying the satisfactory fulfilment of M&Ts.³⁵ At the same time, despite the reinforcement of analytical capacity in its country teams, the Commission's local knowledge and substantive capacity for assessment of national reforms and investments remains inevitably limited compared to that of MSs themselves, especially considering the enormous number of M&Ts in some of the larger Plans: 527 for Italy, 416 for Spain, 372 for Croatia, and 341 for Portugal.³⁶

These structural features of the RRF governance model have given rise to two major practical problems in monitoring and assessing implementation of the NRRPs. Firstly, they have reinforced information asymmetries, which allow for gaming behaviour by MSs, through setting purposely ambiguous or unambitious targets they felt certain of being able to meet, as previously observed in the international academic and policy literature on performance-based financing, which seems to have been largely ignored in the design of the RRF.³⁷ Secondly, they lead to a high level of rigidity in the monitoring and assessment process. Interviewees from nearly all countries studied complain about inflexibility in the Commission's assessment of the fulfilment of M&Ts, exacerbated by the interventions of the ECA, which has been pushing for a more literal and legalistic interpretation of their description in the CIDs. Many MSs which set ambitious targets in their NRRPs warn that they would not do so again in the future, because of the rigid way these are being interpreted.³⁸ National interviewees likewise complain bitterly about the high administrative burden in the verification process, which leads to a loss of ownership and commitment at all levels of governance. Whereas the RRF was supposed to be performance-based, it is now widely perceived as overly bureaucratic, with less flexibility and heavier reporting obligations than the CPF, especially since its good financial management requirements still oblige MSs to drill down to the level of invoices to ensure that the money is being properly spent. But perhaps the worst aspect of the administrative burden created by the RRF monitoring and assessment process is that it does not contribute to improving implementation of the reform and investment projects themselves. While national officials gratefully acknowledge the cooperation of Commission officials in helping to find practical solutions to problems in the assessment process, these interactions, which absorb considerable time and human resources on both sides, typically focus on finding workarounds to formal verification issues rather than on improving substantive achievement of milestones and targets.³⁹

³⁵ See for example ECA, *The Commission's assessment of national recovery and resilience plans* (Special Report 21, Publications Office of the EU, 2022); ECA, *Annual report on the implementation of the EU budget for the 2021 financial year* (Publications Office of the EU, 2022) ch. 10; ECA, *Design of the Commission's control system for the RRF*, (Special report 07 (Publications Office of the EU, 2023)); ECA *Annual report on the implementation of the EU budget for the 2022 financial year* (Publications Office of the European Union, 2023) ch. 11.

³⁶ Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2), 47-48 and Annex 1, Table 2.

³⁷ For examples of such gaming behaviour from Croatia, the Netherlands, and Latvia, see *ibid.* 49. For overviews of the critical international literature on practical experience with performance-based financing elsewhere, see Donald P. Moynihan, and Ian Beazley, *Toward Next-Generation Performance Budgeting: Lessons from the Experience of Seven Reforming Countries* (World Bank, 2016), and Ian Beazley, *Incentivizing Performance in Public Investment Policies Delivered at National and Subnational Levels: Managing across Temporal and Institutional Horizons* (OECD, 2018); for a fuller discussion of this literature, with additional references, see also Zeitlin et al., *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 14-15.

³⁸ *Ibid.* 49-52. In Belgium, the Commission's pressure on the federal government to demonstrate that a recently adopted pension reform will enhance the system's financial sustainability, as specified by the NRRP in language copied from the coalition agreement without much discussion, has delayed the payment request including this milestone, and risks provoking a backlash against the Commission's intervention in domestic political debates reminiscent of similar criticisms during the euro crisis: *ibid.* 51.

³⁹ *Ibid.* 52-53; for an in-depth comparison of the NRRPs and national cohesion programmes, including their performance orientation and reporting requirements, see Zeitlin et al., 'Rethinking the Governance and Delivery Model of the Cohesion Policy Funds' (n 2).

The Commission is aware to some extent of the pushback from MSs on the rigidity and bureaucratization of the monitoring and assessment process. But as officials we interviewed stressed, the RRF is a new instrument, which is still taking shape through learning by doing, where both parties need to adjust to a changed *modus operandi*. Rigidity, in their view, may not always stem from the nature of the instrument itself, but instead from how monitoring requests are interpreted nationally, how administrations coordinate internally, or how milestones are operationalized, among other teething troubles which may be gradually overcome by pragmatism on both sides. The Commission has also been pushing back against the ECA's efforts to further rigidify the RRF monitoring process, including by publishing its own framework for assessing milestones and targets, which emphasizes their broader 'context and purpose' in interpreting MSs' legal obligations.⁴⁰

Beyond these issues of interpretative inflexibility and administrative burden in monitoring and assessing milestones and targets, a crucial limitation of the RRF's performance-based financing model is the difficulty of revising NRRP commitments in the face of unanticipated implementation problems and changes in external circumstances. The RRF Regulation does allow MSs to propose revisions to their NRRPs in the face of unanticipated adverse developments, as all have now taken advantage of additional funding from the REPowerEU programme aimed at reducing dependence on Russian energy.⁴¹ But the threshold for such revisions remains very high, since all changes must be justified in terms of 'objective circumstances', levels of ambition for investments and reforms should not be reduced, and the revised Plan must undergo a full new process of approval by the Commission and the Council, taking account *inter alia* of the most recent CSRs.⁴²

In this context, several of our national interviewees, with long experience in managing complex investment and reform projects, including under the Cohesion Policy Funds, raised principled doubts about the feasibility and effectiveness of maintaining fixed milestones and targets over a six-year period, as envisaged in the NRRPs. There was wide agreement among our national interviewees that any future iteration of the RRF governance model would need to incorporate lighter procedures for monitoring and assessing the fulfilment of milestones and targets, focused more on the underlying purpose of the measures concerned than on their precise description in legally binding texts. Such a revised governance and delivery model would likewise need to include more flexible processes for modifying investment and reform commitments in response not only to unanticipated changes in external circumstances, but also to lessons learned in the course of project implementation itself.⁴³

4. CONCLUSIONS

⁴⁰ Ibid 50, 53, 60-61; ECA *Annual Report 2021* 269-271, 342-343 (Commission replies); COM (2023) 99 final Annex 1; ECA, *Design of the Commission's control system for the RRF* 23; ECA, *Annual report 2022* 343-350, 449-455 (Commission replies).

⁴¹ RRF Regulation (n 9) Art. 21. In response to the high inflation rates resulting from the Russian invasion of Ukraine, many MSs have also requested additional loan support from the RRF: see Commission, 'Overview of Member States' intentions to request RRF loan support' (note to the Council and the European Parliament, 17 April 2023) <<https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2023-04/Overview%20of%20Member%20States%27%20intentions%20to%20request%20RRF%20loan%20support.pdf>>; Zeitlin et al., *Governing the RRF* (n2) 54-55.

⁴² RRF Regulation (n 9) Art. 21. The recent revision of the Italian NRRP, which incorporates numerous changes in measures and M&Ts justified in terms of changes in objective circumstances, along with a new REPowerEU chapter, took nearly four months to negotiate with the Commission, and still needs to be approved by the Council. Exceptionally, the revised Italian Plan includes 43 measures that have been modified 'to implement better alternatives' in order to achieve their original ambition, for which there is no explicit provision in the RRF Regulation. See Commission *Proposal for a Council Implementing Decision amending Implementing Decision (EU) (ST 10160/21; ST 10160/21 ADD 1 REV 2) of 13 July 2021 on the approval of the assessment of the recovery and resilience plan for Italy* COM (2023) 765 final, recitals 11-16.

⁴³ Ibid, 53, 55.

The RRF marks a major new departure in EU governance, with significant effects on domestic policy making in MSs, as well as on relations between national governments and EU institutions. Drawing on detailed comparative research on the drafting, implementation, and monitoring of the NRRPs in eleven MSs (eight primary and three shadow cases), as well as on the broader secondary literature, this chapter has analyzed how the RRF's innovative 'demand-driven, performance-based' governance design has worked in practice and assessed how far it has contributed to advancing the Facility's declared goals, identifying both positive and negative effects. In this concluding section, we weigh up the strengths and weaknesses of the RRF's governance, centred on the NRRPs, and briefly consider its possible implications for future EU policy.

Empirical analysis of the NRRPs clearly shows that the RRF governance design has a number of major *strengths*, as anticipated by its architects within the Commission and the Council. Presented synthetically, seven *key benefits* stand out.

1. The RRF governance design reinforces national ownership and commitment to NRRP objectives by MS governments and other domestic stakeholders.
2. It provides direct financial and policy linkages between reforms and investments.
3. It contributes to improved horizontal and vertical coordination of national policy making.
4. Its performance-based financing system focuses on substantive policy outputs rather than cost-based policy inputs.
5. It promotes the development of more effective European and national structures for monitoring domestic reforms and projects funded from EU sources.
6. It enhances transparency and accountability expectations for national governments to their own publics as well as to the EU on the fulfilment of agreed commitments.
7. It increases leverage for national governments in overcoming domestic opposition to promised reforms.

At the same time, however, as the empirical analysis in this chapter amply demonstrates, the practical operation of the RRF governance design likewise displays a series of fundamental *weaknesses*, some of which could have been predicted from international experience with performance-based financing elsewhere. Here, five major points stand out.

1. The mechanical linkage of payments to the fulfilment of fixed milestones and targets often shifts the attention of both national authorities and the Commission away from the underlying objectives and purpose of reforms and investments to verification and documentation procedures, wasting human resources and sapping ownership at all levels of governance. These negative effects have been exacerbated by bureaucratization and juridification of the monitoring and assessment process under pressure from the ECA.
2. The inflexibility of the performance-based financing and verification system makes it difficult to adjust predetermined milestones and targets in response to unforeseen or changing circumstances and leaves little space for revising and improving projects based on learning from implementation experience. Maintaining fixed milestones and targets in managing innovative projects and complex multiyear plans is neither possible nor productive.
3. Centralization of NRRP drafting under intense time pressure makes it difficult to involve local and regional authorities and other relevant societal stakeholders in the preparation of measures they are responsible for implementing, with negative consequences for both ownership and effectiveness.

4. Reinforcement of leverage for implementing agreed commitments by the RRF's performance-based financing system following a *vincolo esterno* strategy is a double-edged sword. It can empower governments to push through their programmes in the face of political opposition, but it can also offer opportunities for hold-up by veto players, and may yield diminishing returns over time, creating risks of a domestic backlash against the EU.
5. Unclear, non-transparent procedures for ensuring that NRRPs effectively address all, or a significant subset of the CSRs create risks of unequal treatment across MSs.

These weaknesses in the RRF's governance design raise substantial doubts about its fitness for purpose, both now and in the future. A critical question is thus how far these weaknesses could be overcome while retaining the strengths of the current design. Addressing the weaknesses of RRF governance identified in this chapter, while maintaining its benefits in terms of national ownership, coordination, transparency, and accountability, would require in our view a fundamental redesign of its performance-based financing system. Such a redesign would need to move away from the RRF's conception of the NRRPs as a putatively complete contract, based on a commitment by MSs to implement predetermined reforms and investments, operationalized down to specific documents and verification criteria defined in legally binding texts, in exchange for support from the EU budget. Building on the Commission's own recent guidance, such a redesigned performance-based financing system would need to give MSs greater flexibility on the means to achieve the M&Ts, while remaining firm on the underlying objectives and purpose of the investments and reforms they represent. Such a system, in turn, would also require more flexible processes for modifying national investment and reform commitments, in response not only to unanticipated changes in objective circumstances, but also to lessons learned during the course of project implementation itself.⁴⁴

While it remains uncertain whether the RRF will be extended beyond 2026, elements of its governance model seem likely to become an ongoing feature of the EU policy toolkit. Thus, for example, provisions for disbursement of EU funds to MSs based on 'the achievement of results measured by reference to previously set milestones or through performance indicators' had already been added to the EU Financial Regulation in 2018 as part of the preparations for the proposed Reform Support Programme (RSP), one of the RRF's antecedents.⁴⁵ As we noted at the outset, moreover, there are lively debates about extending aspects of the RRF's governance model, including its performance-based financing system, to the CPF and other programmes funded through the EU budget, while national medium-term fiscal-structural plans, which would oblige MS to show how they address the CSRs directed to them, figure prominently in the Commission's recent proposals for the reform of the EU's economic governance framework. Were such proposals to be adopted, it would thus be crucial for the EU to take account of the weaknesses in the RRF governance model revealed

⁴⁴ In our FEPS Policy Study, we develop more specific proposals for revising the RRF's performance-based financing system along these lines through the creation of a multitiered system of 'diagnostic monitoring' by national authorities and the Commission, aimed not only at overseeing whether reform and investment projects are progressing towards timely fulfilment of the agreed M&Ts, but also at assessing what changes may be needed to the initial plan of the measures to take account of problems and possibilities for improvement uncovered during the implementation process: see Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 15, 61-62; and for an application to reform of the CPF, Zeitlin et al. 'Rethinking the Governance and Delivery Model of the Cohesion Policy Funds' (n 2) 27-30. On the concept of diagnostic monitoring, see also Charles F. Sabel 'Diagnostic Monitoring: An Overview with Application to Smart Specialization', note prepared for Commission, DG REGIO (June 2016). Other recommendations for revising the RRF governance model advanced in our FEPS study include making effective inclusion of key domestic stakeholders in the drafting and implementation of National Plans a binding assessment criterion for approval of plans and payment requests, and establishing explicit and transparent procedures for ensuring that such Plans address all or a significant subset of CSRs. See Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 63.

⁴⁵ Päivi Leino-Sandberg, 'Recovery and Resilience Facility two years after – quo vadis EU money?' (28 September 2023) <verfassungsblog.de/recovery-and-resilience-facility-two-years-after-quo-vadis-eu/money>.

by the practical experience of drafting, implementing, and monitoring the NRRPs, most notably by revising its performance-based financing system.⁴⁶

⁴⁶ For a fuller discussion of the implications of experience with the RRF for reform of the EU economic governance framework and the CPF, see Zeitlin et al. *Governing the RRF* (n 2) 64-5; Zeitlin et al. 'Rethinking the Governance and Delivery Model of the Cohesion Policy Funds'.